

TO THE WATERS AND THE WILD: BUILDING A VISUAL DEVELOPMENTAL PORTFOLIO

by

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I. Introduction

This portfolio started as something completely different to what I had wanted it to be. Although, I suppose that is a key part of any developmental process. Originally, the portfolio was supposed to be centered around environment paintings—creating pieces that are a part of the same basic time period and architectural and environmental influence. However, as I found myself deep into numerous sketches of Viking long houses, deep forest clearings, and mysterious stone structures, a story began to form in my mind.

Having grown up reading old Scandinavian and Celtic fables, the idea of an isolated Viking village that had to constantly encounter and deal with mythological monsters and creatures (an everyday occurrence that has always seemed like quite the nuisance for the more common folk of a fairy tale). These villagers would see river monsters and forest curses as just another thing to deal with in their unmistakably difficult lives. The idea of child rearing and business management would seem daunting under the ever-present threat of child snatching fairies and trouble making Nixies.

This amusing sentiment led me to develop a deeper world of villagers and conflicts and resistance to magical sabotage. The character through which I wanted to present this interaction was an impartial, almost inconsequential firefly—one who would dwell both in the forest and among the humans as they make their nightly luminating sojourn through the village clearing. However, as the story progressed and I realized I needed a character who could communicate and interact with these mythological creatures, the main character shifted to a small Viking girl who frequently aids the more harmless creatures who reside around the village.

My art process for this development ranged from scenes and characters that seemed to draw themselves, to creatures that just never seemed right no matter how many redesigns they went through. Having specialized in visual development for backgrounds and layouts, I did not think much on character design. However, as the story became more involved and

character-driven, I knew that these characters needed to have a specific style and a unique look to make them stand out in the portfolio. The following is a written outline describing the development of the characters and overall plot—a way of getting these ideas down before the art even started.

II. Story Structure Development

Genre: Fantasy

Premise/Logline: A small viking girl and her firefly companion are led into the woods surrounding her village by a forest spirit and they encounter creatures from Scandinavian, Icelandic & Celtic mythology, while stumbling upon the darker secrets of the woods and the creatures that live there.

Main Character/Description: Toril “Tor” – a small, wild mannered girl, around 8 years old, who earns her keep around the village and the reluctant acceptance of the other villagers by doing anything and everything that needs to be done. The daughter of a local fisherman, who has clear disdain for the young girl. She has blonde, choppy hair that hangs in her face, and is not in the least bit bothered by this fact. She is skinny and nimble, wearing messily thrown together clothes made of old cloth that hang off of her, too large and quite ill-fitting, as no villager has ever bothered to give the girl much aid in this department. Children of the village are raised through the group effort of all of the villagers, as it is a small community, but they are reluctant to raise this girl who is prone to mischief and frequently seeks the company of creatures such as house brownies and nixies.

Tor is quick to anger, speaks very little (when she is inclined to make any sort of conversation, it would only be to her ever-faithful but terribly moody firefly companion), and keeps to herself (first due to the general dislike from the other villagers, and then from a more voluntary, purposeful intention on the girl’s part). This is not to say, however, that the girl is rude

(or at least she doesn't think she is), she has simply forgone any attempt to learn proper etiquette. Often found barefoot (to keep up the appearance of savage inclinations and, simply because shoes are often too big and terribly uncomfortable), Tor has a penchant for the mischievous, but is not so foolhardy as to show it in front of the villagers.

Tor also has (or, is cursed with, in her opinion) the ability to see mythological creatures – the ones who hide themselves from the humans, from common house brownies to the terrifying *Fossegrimen* whose bright red eyes stare out at her from the surface of the river. This, along with her more wild tendencies, leaves her ostracized from the rest of the villagers, who fear any interaction with the faerie folk and believe Toril will only bring them misfortune. Tor frequently interacts with these creatures (they're some of the only beings that acknowledge her presence), completing tasks for them and helping them with any issues they might have (even the more terrifying ones, she's learned not to judge by appearances (except the *Fossegrimen*, she draws the line at that one.)). She keeps her hair long and in front of her face quite often – to avoid making eye contact with some of the more dangerous beings that dwell in the forest or the lake.

Characteristics/Attribute list:

Mischievous – a sucker for a good adventure

Orphaned – parents unknown (and will probably stay unknown or unimportant)

Quiet Introverted

Short tempered Curious

Hardworking Clever

Easily exploited Overworked

Tough Small/slight (underfed)

Adventurous Cynical

Versatile Resourceful

Full of repressed rage

Terrified of the river (and the Fossegrimen who dwells within it)

Status Quo: A quiet, isolated, village of Scandinavian influence, surrounded by a forest on one side and a river on the other that runs back into the forest. Toril spends her days doing mindless chores for the inhabitants of the village, earning her keep at the small fishing shack by the riverbed by completing the jobs that nobody wants to do or, rather, any jobs that could be feasibly accomplished by a 7-8 year old child. Her only companion is a lone firefly who prefers the girl's company to that of other fireflies.

Tor frequently runs into forest sprites and faeries (in Norse mythology: huldre folk) who offer her presents in exchange for her help. Gnomes and smaller, more friendly creatures are especially fond of the girl. They are not as fond of the firefly (a sentiment shared by the coruscating insect).

Point of Attack/Inciting Incident: Tor runs into a forest spirit (think Will O' the Wisp) that attempts to lure her further into the forest as she is out foraging for food and bait for fishing. She finds herself deep into the forest and encounters some far more powerful huldre who aim to get her to do their bidding and/or take her life through a series of underhanded deals and miscellaneous tasks. These creatures believe that they are deceiving the girl, but she seems to outwit them every time, nearly escaping the more fatal deals, finding loopholes in their rules and ensuring that her end of the deals are upheld and unbreaking.

Main Conflict: Eventually, one of her "deals" with one of the more powerful Huldre goes astray and she releases a very powerful and dangerous creature that had been trapped by the other Huldre, believing that this creature would then go on to help her escape her miserable life in the village. This shadow creature had been bound into a corporeal form by a binding spell which, once broken by the girl, allows him to wreak havoc upon the forest. (The binding spell is only able to be broken by a non-magical being.) Word gets out among the other creatures about what Tor has done and her ability to see hidden beings/free them and she is hunted down by all manner of creatures as she makes her way through the forest. The shadow creature that has been released has full dominion over the forest and revels in creating chaos and destruction among the

faerie folk. Because of the creature's power, Toril is trapped in the forest where she is being constantly hunted by the huldre.

The creatures going after her either want to kill her to keep her from intervening with faerie business, or they want her to do something that only a non-magical creature can do (such as break curses or intervene further into matters protected from those who possess magic). Tor encounters a variety of magical beings, from inhuman demi-gods to the giant trolls of the forest as she flees from those who wish to use her. However, the deeper parts of the forest are full of faerie mischief in the form of hidden mazes, trapped paths, and deceptive figures or forms that lead only to an untimely death.

Resolution: Tor's releasing of the dangerous shadow creature binds her to the forest, and she finds she cannot escape the woods no matter which direction she travels. The shadow creature greatly upsets the balance of the Huldre. Toril encounters a member of the Seelie Court that demands she do something about the shadow creature, explaining that there is a legend about a binding object that could once again hold the beast within a form. Toril then undergoes a series of tasks/trials that enable her to obtain a magical rope made of vines and foliage which, once placed on a host, binds the shadow creature to them. After summoning the shadow creature and tricking him into making another deal with her, Toril binds him to herself – fixing the balance of power in the forest and ensuring that the shadow creature is rendered powerless for as long as he's bound to her. Toril finds her place in between both the world of the Huldre and the humans, taking on a role as a protector of balance and an intermediary to the Faerie courts and the humans.

Outline of the Trials:

Trial 1:

Solve the riddle of the Bogle

Bogles are notorious for confusing travelers - and this riddle that needs to be solved is hardly a riddle at all.

Trial 2:

Retrieve an object from the guarded garden

Found in the glamoured realm of the Pishogue Pooka

Trial 3:

Take the heart of a creature, plant it in the fairy circle, and give the flower to the Old Hag of the forest

The old hag gives Toril a key in return that unlocks the binding object

World of Your Story

Period of your story: If it were set on Earth as we know it, then it would be sometime during the Middle Ages, during the Viking Age (793 - 1066 AD). However, this is an alternate - Earth/Fantasy world — the kind where magic exists and is known by its inhabitants. Mythology is more historical record than fiction and is firmly believed by every being.

Primary Setting of your story: A small Viking village that rests on a hillside, surrounded by forest and a river on either side. The village is very isolated and has little to no interaction with the outside world or other Viking villages.

What are the distinguishing features of your world?

The village and its surrounding forest (as very little of the world is really seen other than this) is comprised of smaller, practical houses made from wooden beams, packed sod roofs, and wooden pillars carved with images similar to that of Viking carvings of snakes and dragons, but with much more of a mythological-based subject matter (the carvings will cover a wide range of mythical species that inhabit the forest). The village is not prosperous, but it is able to feed its people and maintain a steady population. Most of their efforts are placed into logging, foraging,

and fishing. Although, no villager dares to go very far into the forest for fear of the larger, more menacing creatures that might be encountered in the darker parts of the forest.

Are there special rules in the world of your story that viewers need to understand?

As stated above, magic does exist and is acknowledged in the daily lives of these villagers, mythical creatures are very much a reality, but are very rarely seen or interacted with. Magic exists in nature and in these creatures, but is not known to have ever been associated with any human person (there are no witches and/or warlocks who live in the woods, is what I'm getting at).

Wisps, if one is entirely unaware, are notoriously mischievous creatures, and are some of the only mythical beings that actively seek to interfere or interact with humans. They are known to lead to either treasure, if luck is on the followers side, or to your doom — depending on the type of day they've had.

Some humans are able to see these creatures better than others, as many faerie folk (or *Huldufólk* according to Scandinavian mythology) and creatures choose to remain hidden from humans (who are notoriously meddlesome and are, sometimes, too clever even for the tricks of the faeries).

Those who can see every creature are rare, but not unheard of, and are often the cause of many catastrophic events that can occur when humans interfere with the huldre. These individuals do not possess any magic, however. The sight is merely like a strange and rare mutation - like color blindness but rarer.

Main Character Environment

ABOUT YOUR MAIN CHARACTER'S ENVIRONMENT

Main Character Home (apartment, hovel, dorm): Tor lives in an old fishing shack, after having been taken in by a cranky old fisherman, who was in need of an assistant/apprentice when

she was found as a child. She is expected to take up as little space as possible, and is provided with very few amenities or possessions of her own.

Who does your Main Character live with (including pets)?/Does he or she like who he's

living with?: The Oooooo' Fisherman. He's her main caretaker, although that term can be used very loosely in regard to how he treats Tor — who hates his fishy guts. Mainly because he threatens to drown her in the river at the first sign of trouble. He's not a nice man. Or a very good fisher.

She also has a companion (not a pet) firefly, who lives with her. He even has a little bed of his own (at his own insistence). She likes the firefly much more than the fisherman.

Name 5 things in Your Main Character's home that reveals character:

- 1) A general lack of belongings
- 2) A bed that is made from an old sail and a very flat pillow she, ahem, *borrowed* from one of the other children
- 3) An extensive collection of rocks and shiny objects and other pieces of interesting scraps that she hides in a bag under the floorboard.
- 4) A smaller bed made for her not-so-trusty firefly companion
- 5) Small metal knife taken while the fisherman wasn't looking and stored in a super secret place (also under the floorboards)

Name your Main Character's 3 most treasured possessions:

- 1) Tor wears a small wooden charm with the rune *Laguz* carved into it. A small gnome who lives in a shrub gave it to her. They like to collect charms, and Tor saved him from a rather aggressive chicken. It's the only gift she's ever gotten.
 - a) The *Laguz* charm, for reference, symbolizes formlessness, chaos, unconscious growth, and living energy. It is a protection rune, especially for travelers/adventurers.
- 2) Tor collects nice rocks. She can use them to bargain with some of the more friendly *huldre*. Her favorite one turns bright green in the water of a nearby pond.
- 3) The knife she keeps hidden. For protection.

How did your main character “decorate” his/her home?:

Tor's not really permitted to decorate her space. The fisherman doesn't like “junk” unless it's *his* junk. She has a small place in the forest, though, that she is able to visit from time to time. Made from a large piece of tree bark and a few conveniently placed boulders. That is stocked full of small trinkets she's gotten from friendly creatures and more nice rocks. It's also covered in picked wildflowers and things nicked from some of the more rude residents of the village.

What is your main character's neighborhood like?:

It's a *small* village. Everyone knows everyone, and everybody's business is known by everybody. It is mainly a fishing village, with some use of forest foraging and hunting for food and building supplies. The village is isolated for miles from any other settlement, and rarely gets visitors or any sort of traveling tradesmen. The village is built on a small hillside, surrounded by a river and forest. There are frequent festivals and parties for miscellaneous holidays and religious celebrations (as a break from the suffocating monotony of doing the exact same thing every day and to take their minds off of the harsh cold and unrelenting darkness of the winter months).

Supporting Character/Description:

Baugi is a fairly normal firefly, and he is very proud of that fact. In his opinion, he was rudely ostracized by the other fireflies with whom he used to associate with (NOT his family—not after they cast him out). If he were being honest, he has times in which he does sometimes struggle to control his luminescent posterior, which may have created a little, tiny bit of havoc within the firefly community, which relies heavily upon their ability to communicate through their light. As such, Baugi (entirely of his own choosing, thank you very much) left the colony and found refuge in a small human village in a forest clearing. In doing so, he meets Toril—a fellow outcast (except her posterior lacks any ability to glow entirely).

BAUGI Characteristics/Attributes:**Hot-tempered**

Loyal

Outcast

Fiery

EMOTIONAL

Has *ahem* lighting issues (don't mention it)

Irritable

Protective

Easily tired

Opinionated

Untrusting of strangers A bit simple

Creatures List/Bestiary:

- **Skogsra** - wild female forest spirit
- **Huldra** - forest sirens (a member of the forest *rá* – keepers or wardens of the forest)
 - Not to be confused with the common term *Huldre*, which encompasses most magical forest creatures.
- **Sjörå** or havsfru - aquatic sirens (similar to mermaids) (a member of the forest *rá*)
- **Bergsrå** - cave dwellers who interfere with mining activity (a member of the forest *rá*)
- **Nøkken** - a mystical troll-like creature/deep lake monster who is capable of shape-shifting. Lures innocent people to his kingdom at the bottom of the lake
- **Elves** - (both dark and light) or faeries (Seelie and Unseelie)
- **Trolls** - giants of the forest that protect sacred spaces; turn to stone in the sunlight; frightened away by lightning
- **Gnomes** - tiny, mostly harmless tricksters, who dwell near human settlements
- **Nissen** - small, gnome-like pranksters that live in barns (but give gifts if befriended)
- **Tusser** - mischievous underground goblins (do not approach)
- **Wisps** - also called *aarnivalkea*; lead humans to either treasure or danger - impossible to tell which until it's too late. Mischievous creatures of blue flame
- **Draugar** - undead (uncommon unless some faerie has taken up necromancy); superior strength; guards treasure they were buried with
- **The Mare** - a malicious creature known to give people nightmares by sitting on their chests as they slept; thought to be the embodiment of the souls of living people who left their bodies in the night

- **The Lamia** - seductive faerie woman who lures men in with the promise of pleasure and sucks their life's vitality, leaving behind empty husks
- **Nixies** - river dwelling faeries who are enchanting to look upon, but will drown anyone who spies on them at play
- **Jack-in-Irons** - assaults travelers on secluded forest roads/paths
- **Red-caps** - keep their vitality from dying their hats in human/animal blood
- **Changelings** - a faerie form that resembles a child but is instead an old goblin or a rotten piece of wood put in place of a stolen human child
- **Nienivin/Unseelie Queen** - ruler over dusk and darkness; rules over those in the Unseelie court (more a force of nature/a shadow of a being rather than an actual figure) Also known as *Berchta* or *Elph Queine of the Unseelie Court*
- **Black Annis** - the blue-faced hag, sits upon a log and grinds her long white teeth
- **Hobgoblins** (bauchans & bwbachs) - mischief makers; household faeries that do odd jobs around the house in the night - but only for compensation
- **Bogles** - mischief maker; more solitary; exist for the sole purpose of perplexing mankind
- **The Foul Faery** - lurks within the darkest recesses of the forest, luring its victims in with a sticky web, glamoured to look unthreatening and safe (a bed of flowers/a clear pond). Once in its web, the faery takes over a human soul. It fears sunlight.
- **The Sink Bodach** - a malodorous creature that lives in tubs, sinks, buckets, and ponds
- **The Death Faery** - also known as a Banshee or the Washer at the Ford, foretells death, can only be seen/heard by those close to death
- **The Fideal** - wanders the edges of lakes at twilight singing/calling out to her lover, an irresistible song that lures many mortals with her under the waters, where they are choked by reeds
- **Pishogue (Glamour) Pooka** - small creature, a master of glamour, illusion, and delusion, distorts reality and truth
- **Hobyah** - a creature that is created/sustained from fear, often found dwelling in children's closets or under their beds. The smallest positive thought banishes them.

Faerie Lore/Forest Encounters:

*The world in which this story takes place is influenced heavily by ancient Scandinavian people and the mythology that developed to explain the world around them. However, it also includes creatures, traditions, and rules for its magic that are inspired by folklore from other cultures and people. Faeries, as a general term, can be found as a part of cultures and folklore all over the world.

Creation:

Not much is known about the Faerie folk on the human's behalf, however, it is said that the two factions of Faerie (or Huldre) came about from the transmutation of maggots from the dead body of the giant Ymir, the first being that came into creation. These maggots eventually formed into light and dark elves, which are then divided into courts - the Seelie and the Unseelie Courts, respectively. Although these faeries are divided by dark and light, good and bad, all Huldre have the potential for goodness or terrible destruction, changing according to circumstance, or on a whim. The actions of the Huldre hold this world in a tensioned balance, usually only thrown off at the interference of non magical mortals, from which they tend to remain hidden.

Faerie/Huldre Encounters Within the Story:

- The earliest interactions that Toril has with the Huldre folk are within the village. Because the Faerie can remain unseen by most mortals, they can often make their way into the village, manipulating moods, actions, and thoughts of the inhabitants. Bogey's, for instance, leaps onto the backs of mortals and affixes itself with sharp talons, urging their human puppets to act unnaturally or cause mischief. Pooks, similarly, will throw glamours over false words, making them seem plausible or true. Toril is able to see these creatures on some of the villagers and her attempts to ward them off receive anything from strange looks to serious scoldings from those around her.
- Toril is often faced with hobgoblins, brownies, Nissen, gnomes, and other faery creatures that like to dwell in or around mortal settlements. These creatures are harmless if they are

respected (mainly in the form of gifts/food left out for them) and often help Toril out with chores or offer her small gifts.

III. Art Process/Methods

Step 1: Quick, loose sketches. For environments, the shapes are blocked out, making sure the eye follows where it should (focus is on composition). For creatures, shape is emphasized first (focus is on silhouette) and then color as form is more defined.

Step 2: Value render. Sketch is blocked in with 3-4 grey scale values, with white being the brightest indication of light. From this, mood, lighting, and composition focus is established (mainly for environments or key scenes).

Step 3: Color render. Grey scale value is painted over with a color scheme that is used to convey emotion, mood, and time of day within the scene.

Artwork: Early Development

Artwork: Final Character Design

Toril

CHARACTER CONCEPT/EXPRESSION SHEET

Baugi the Firefly CHARACTER CONCEPT/EXPRESSION SHEET

Will the Wisp CHARACTER CONCEPT/EXPRESSION SHEET

The girl needed to be scrappy - as one does to survive this particular forest. Small, nimble, almost malnourished with choppy blonde hair and a worrying lack of footwear, Toril dons a red, Brothers Grimm-esque tunic, intentionally making her stand out from the dark greens

and blues of the forest. Each character is color coded in an effort to provide contrast, as well as an insight into their character, personality and role within the story.

Although character design wasn't a priority for me going into this portfolio, I quickly realized that a story focused on a fantasy forest full of mythological creatures would need, feasibly, some creatures with which to fill it. Therefore, I (begrudgingly, at first) began a series of Bestiary pages—pages illustrating and describing the creatures that Toril might encounter on her adventures. The creature design was based on basic shapes that would allude to their personalities and their role within their environments. My first creature, the Bark Goblin, loosely designed on the goblins and Bogles of both Scandinavian and Celtic mythology, adorns itself with bark, therefore its design was based on very spiky, stiff, and triangular shapes. The river-dwelling Mudpin, in contrast, reflected smoother, circular shapes that would be favorable to an aquatic environment. I wanted the focus of these designs to be environment and personality based. Their forms should make sense to the viewer for how they live and collect food while also communicating their individual attitudes and character.

Artwork: Bestiary Pages

RED CAP

BLOODTHIRSTY AND CUNNING, THE RED CAP FAERY THRIVES IN DARK, WET TUNNELS AND HOLES. BLOOD IS THEIR MAIN SOURCE OF NUTRIENTS. SOAKED THROUGH THE SKIN AS THEIR NAME SUGGESTS, ALL RED CAPS POSSESS A HEAD COVERING USED TO SOAK UP THE BLOOD OF THEIR PREY - UTILIZING THE CAP AS A CONTINUOUS SOURCE OF BLOOD. ALTHOUGH THEY ARE ABLE TO SURVIVE WITHOUT THIS MANDY GARMENT, THE CONSTANT NEED FOR BLOOD MAKES THEIR EXISTENCE DIFFICULT TO MAINTAIN WITHOUT IT.

To the Waters & the Wild - Bestiary

MUDPIN - RIVER IMP

THE MUDPIN IS A CURIOUS CREATURE, DWELLING AMONG LAKE BEDS AND FOREST STREAMS. SEMI-AQUATIC, THEY MAKE THEIR HOMES OUT OF MUD, WITH THEIR DIET CONSISTING OF SMALL FISH AND A MIX OF WORMS AND GRUBS. ALTHOUGH THESE RIVER IMPS POSE LITTLE REAL THREAT, THEY ARE EASILY AGGRAVATED AND WILL BITE WHEN FEELING THREATENED. CAUTIOUSLY CURIOUS BEINGS, THE RIVER IMPS WILL FOLLOW HUMANS THEY DEEM INTERESTING, MAINTAINING A SHORT DISTANCE. IT IS NOT UNCOMMON TO HEAR THE SLAP OF MUDPIN FEET BEHIND YOU IF WANDERING NEAR STREAMS OR PONDS.

DIET CONSISTS OF MAINLY FISH & WORMS

To the Waters & the Wild - Bestiary

Bergsrå

These cave dwelling collectors spend most of their lives digging out small underground tunnels, determining the quality of the rocks and ores that they uncover. Upon meeting certain criteria, the material is stored on their back and used for "trade" with local miners. It is not uncommon to find something missing from one's pack when taking shelter in a cave where these creatures dwell. But rest assured, for there will almost always be a nice rock in place of the pilloined object.

SKIN HAS ROCK-LIKE TEXTURE
HAIR MADE OF MOSSY VEGETATION

ROCKS AND VALUABLES
STORED IN PACK

Artwork: Mood Paintings

Artwork: Key Scene Paintings

Artwork: Village Map

The story starts in a small Viking village surrounded by a dense forest. As the characters wander farther into the forest, the story becomes darker, with emphasis on color only where the light breaks through. The key scene paintings within the forest are vivid and full of contrasting shadow, while the scenes in the village are unsaturated, almost grey-toned. The shift to dramatic, vivid colors echoes the path the girl takes farther into the unnatural and surreal atmosphere of the forest.

The purpose of concept art is to create a visual look and feel to the story - to present the style and color scheme in which the audience will experience the story as it unfolds. Although this style can eventually change or evolve further into the production process, the visual development art sets the initial standard for design and style.

Artwork: Architecture Development

The Fishing Shack

Architecture Study: The Tree House

III. Conclusion

The main purpose of this portfolio was to create a series of visual development art that could be combined into a professional demonstration of my skills and style, while also maintaining a visual coherency throughout each piece. However, as the project progressed, I found myself delving deeper into the story, the characters, and the creatures themselves. What was simply a way to demonstrate skill within the field of visual development became an entire world that I am sure will continue to influence and inspire my work in the future.